

Comparison at 7T of the Impulse head gradient and whole-body SC72 gradient transfer functions

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Synopsis

Motivation: Ultra-high field MRI requires high performance and fidelity gradients to push forward the spatio-temporal resolution, especially for fMRI scans.

Goal: Compare two commercial gradient coils (whole-body SC72 and head-only Impulse) available on 7T scanners.

Approach: Characterization of the gradient transfer function (GTF) and measurement of field perturbations following a spoiler gradient using a field camera.

Results: The Impulse gradient revealed a smooth GTF profile while the SC72 exhibited strong resonances. Field oscillations following a spoiler gradient were greatly reduced with the Impulse gradient. Disconnecting the 3rd order shim coils on the SC72 improved also the quality of its response.

Impact: The GTF of the Impulse gradient coil yields interesting prospects. It remains to be determined whether the apparent benefits versus the SC72 are due to the absence of third order shim coils.

Abstract

Introduction

The race towards higher spatio-temporal resolution in MRI calls for stronger static magnetic fields and gradients with higher slew rates and amplitudes. It results in complex magneto-mechanical coupling between the gradient and the magnet that can lead to hardware damage or image artefacts, especially on EPI acquisitions. In addition, more powerful gradients require new designs in order to comply with the physiological limits, such as the recently developed Impulse head gradient [1] that allows reaching 200mT/m amplitude and 900mT/m/ms slew rate, versus 80mT/m amplitude and 200mT/m/ms slew rate for the standard SC72 whole-body gradient integrated in most state-of-the-art Siemens 7T scanners. The goal here was to compare the Gradient Transfer Functions (GTF) of these two systems.

Methods

Measurements were performed on two Terra scanner systems (Siemens Healthcare AG, Erlangen, Germany) respectively equipped with the SC72 whole-body (MNI, Montreal, Canada) and Impulse (Berkeley, CA, USA) gradients (Table 1). The GTF was estimated on the two systems using a field camera (Skope MRT, Zürich, Switzerland) [2,3]. For visualization of the potential consequences of the peaks and dips in the GTF, B_0 and G_z oscillations following the application of a spoiler gradient were also measured. The gradient was played along the Z axis and had an amplitude ranging from 10mT/m to 39mT/m, a duration of 650 μ s and a plateau of 210 μ s. Measurements on the SC72 gradient were performed in two different configurations: with the third order shim coils connected and disconnected at the filter plate inside the Faraday cage. The Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) of the GPAs was tuned for each scenario.

Results

Figure 1 shows that the strong peaks/dips observed on the SC72 gradient (X, Y and Z axes) were greatly reduced on both the magnitude and phase of the GTF spectrum when disconnecting the third order

shim coils at the filter plate. Although some resonances were also visible on the Impulse GTF, they were located at slightly higher frequencies, thus more difficult to excite with imaging gradients. Overall, the GTF of the Impulse gradient exhibited less severe resonances.

Figure 2 shows an example of the consequences of imperfect GTF in the time-domain. The spoiler gradients, as usually found in the MPRAGE sequence for instance, here on the Z axis excite a wide range of frequencies that make B_0 and G_z oscillate for some time following their application. On the SC72 gradient coil, these oscillations had a main frequency of 1350 Hz, corresponding to a mechanical resonance on the gradient Z axis visible in the GTF on Figure 1 (top left) [4], and lasted for tens of milliseconds for both G_z and B_0 . After the spoiler gradient of 39mT/m, G_z oscillations were on the order of 0.05mT/m when the third order shim was connected. The G_z oscillations were attenuated by more than 3-fold when the third order shim coils were disconnected. Such reduction of the B_0 field was however not visible in that configuration. Oscillations were considerably reduced on the Impulse gradient coil.

Discussion

The Impulse gradient coil revealed less field oscillations, especially regarding B_0 , compared to the SC72 gradient coil where they persisted for tens of milliseconds as shown before [5]. The spoiler measurements here focused on the Z axis, which is the most problematic axis on the SC72 gradient due to a strong mechanical resonance at 1350Hz [4]. Attenuation of the oscillations with the SC72 gradient when disconnecting the third order shim coils at the filter plate inside the Faraday cage is the subject of an ongoing investigation. At the time of the measurement, the Impulse head gradient coil of the NexGen 7T scanner did not embed third order shim coils at all, which could possibly explain some of the apparent benefits versus the SC72. Imperfections in the GTF spectrum are problematic when resonances are excited, for instance when applying strong spoiler gradients or when the echo-spacing of an EPI train is set to one of these specific frequencies. Deviations from the nominal gradient waveform occurring during a gradient readout can be corrected for in the reconstruction [6,7]. When they occur during an RF excitation, e.g. following a spoiler gradient, they may interfere with the RF pulses and lower their performance.

Conclusion

The GTF of the Impulse gradient coil yields interesting prospects. It remains to be determined whether the apparent benefits versus the SC72 are due to the absence of third order shim coils.

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References

1. Davids M, Dietz P, Ruyters G, Roesler M, Klein V, Guérin B, Feinberg DA, Wald LL. Peripheral nerve stimulation informed design of a high-performance asymmetric head gradient coil. *Magn Reson Med* 2023.
2. Barmet C, De Zanche N, Pruessmann K. P. Spatiotemporal magnetic field monitoring for MR. *Magn Reson Med* 2008; 60:187-197.
3. Vannesjo SJ, Haeberlin M, Kasper L, Pavan M, Wilm BJ, Barmet C, Pruessmann KP. Gradient system characterization by impulse response measurements with a dynamic field camera. *Magn Reson Med* 2013; 69: 583-593.
4. Boulant N, Quettier L et al. Commissioning of the Iseult CEA 11.7 T whole-body MRI: current status, gradient-magnet interaction tests and first imaging experience. *MAGMA* 2023 Apr;36(2):175-189. doi: 10.1007/s10334-023-01063-5.
5. Scholten H, Lohr D, Wech T, Köstler H. Fast measurement of the gradient system transfer function at 7T. *Magn Reson Med* 20223;89:1644-1659.

6. Vannesjo SJ, Graedel NN, Kasper L, Gross S, Busch J, Haeberlin M, Barmet C, Pruessmann KP. Image reconstruction using a gradient impulse response model for trajectory prediction. *Magn Reson Med* 2016;76:45-58.
7. Vannesjo SJ, Duerst Y, Vionnet L, Dietrich BE, Pavan M, Gross S, Barmet C, Pruessmann KP. Gradient and shim pre-emphasis by inversion of a linear time-invariant system model. *Magn Reson Med* 2017;78:1607-1622

	SC72	Impulse
Weight	900 kg	1060 kg
Length	1.59 m	1.19 m
Inner / outer diameter	64 / 81 cm	44 / 81 cm
Inductance over X / Y / Z	870/845/820 μ H	315/383/315 μ H
DC resistance over X / Y / Z	140/130/135 m Ω	55/59/48 m Ω
Maximum gradient strength	80 mT/m	200 mT/m
Maximum slew rate	200 mT/m/ms	900 mT/m/ms

Table 1: Characteristics of the two gradient coils (whole-body SC72 and head Impulse coils) compared in the current study.

Figure 1. Magnitude (top row) and phase (bottom row) of the self-terms of the GTF spectrum for the whole-body SC72 gradient coil with the third order shim connected or disconnected at the filter plate (inside the Faraday cage), and for the Impulse head gradient coil. Phase results are presented with a detrending over the -5 to 5 kHz window for comparison purposes. The SC72 gradient had a strong resonance peak at 1350Hz that was greatly reduced when disconnecting the third order shim. The Impulse gradient had a smoother spectrum.

Figure 2. a) Spoiler gradients were played along the Z axis with amplitudes of 10mT/m to 39mT/m, a duration of 650 μ s and 210 μ s-plateaus. b) These gradient shapes excite a wide range of frequencies. c) After the spoiler, field measurement reveals G_Z and B_0 oscillations lasting for tens of milliseconds with a main frequency of 1350Hz for the SC72 gradient. They were largely attenuated on G_Z when unplugging the third order shim at the filter plate. The Impulse gradient had an oscillation at 1750Hz that attenuated more rapidly and was more robust regarding B_0 oscillations.